

Biophysical studies on the molecular chaperone function, structure and interaction of eye lens protein α -crystallin – A Review[†]

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Abstract : α -Crystallin is the major constituent protein of the eye lens of the vertebrates. It is an oligomeric protein having micelle like architecture. Ever since it was reported in early 90's that it possesses molecular chaperone like function which is crucial for the maintenance of the transparency of the eye lens, interests in understanding the mechanism of such function developed rapidly. Various laboratories have contributed towards understanding of the structure and function of this protein. Our group has been engaged to study specific problems related to this area. We undertook detailed study to understand the structure of bound substrates employing a combination of simple molecular biology and biophysical tools to show that α -crystallin recognizes early folding intermediates and bound substrates have native-like structure. Our work showed that chaperone activity correlated fairly well with exposed surface hydrophobicity. We proved that temperature activation was not required for α -crystallin to function as chaperone as was proposed by others. Very importantly we demonstrated that some small molecules such as ATP can interact with α -crystallin to form weak associated chaperone-substrate complex that can play crucial role in increasing the thermodynamic stability and chaperone function and refractive properties of the lens. Some bivalent metal ions such as Zn^{2+} plays a very important role in the structure, stability and chaperone function of α -crystallin and such a sore has considerable physiological significance in understanding the cataract formation in the lens. This article is not intended to be a comprehensive account of all aspects of work done on this protein. But instead in this article we have reviewed primarily our work and mentioned the work done by others in these specific areas only.

Keywords : α -Crystallin, molecular chaperone, eye lens protein, protein-protein interaction, thermal aggregation, hydrophobicity, subunit exchange, structural recognition, binding sites.

1. Introduction

1.1. α -Crystallin and the eye lens

Eyes is an extremely complex optical system that creates the image, converts the image into a set of electrical signals and transmits these signals to brain through neuronal pathway via the optic nerve¹. Lens is a transparent biconvex structure in the eye whose function is to act as

a refractive medium to focus light on to the retina². The lens is the part of the anterior segment of the eye located behind the iris which controls the amount of light that enters in to the eye. It is kept wet by aqueous humor on one side and by the vitreous body on the other side. Eye lens is composed of 65% water and 35% proteins³. Crystallins are a group of proteins found in the eye lens of vertebrates that constitute nearly 90% of its proteins⁴.

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In human eye lens the common constituents are α -, β - and γ -crystallin. Birds and reptiles contain another protein called δ -crystallin^{5,6}. These are water soluble proteins that pack tightly in the lens to a very high concentration (>400 mg/ml) to produce the refractive medium. α -Crystallin constitutes ~45% of the total lens protein and the other 55% is constituted by β - and γ -crystallin.

α -Crystallin is composed of two types of subunit α A- and α B-, which associate non-covalently to form a heterogeneous oligomers^{7,8} of average molecular weight 800 kDa. Each subunit is roughly 20 kDa with α A- and α B-crystallin having 173 and 175 residues in human lens⁹. In human eye α A- and α B-crystallin exists in the ratio¹⁰ of 3 : 1. The oligomer of α -crystallin is a dynamic entity from which subunits are constantly associating and dissociating¹¹⁻¹⁴. Initially it was believed that the expression of α -crystallin was limited to the eye lens only. But later it was found to be present in small quantities in many other organs including heart, skeletal muscle, spleen, thymus, retina, kidney and brain¹⁵⁻¹⁸. This suggested that this protein might have a more general role in cellular function. The expression of α B-crystallin has been associated with various neurodegenerative diseases such as Alexander's disease¹⁵, Lewy body disease¹⁹, Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease^{20,21} and Alzheimer's disease¹⁷. α -Crystallin was found to be a member of the small heat shock protein (sHSP) family²²⁻²⁵. sHSPs are abundant both in eukaryotic and prokaryotic organisms and their functional similarities are conserved from bacteria to humans⁹. Both α A- and α B-crystallin is known to provide cellular thermoresistance^{26,27}. α B-Crystallin is known to be induced by oxidative stress or heat shock^{23,28}.

1.2. Structure and sequence of α -crystallin

Amino acid sequence of human and bovine α -crystallin was established^{29,30} in early 1970s. Bovine and human α -crystallin bears nearly 75% sequence homology between them. Many other mammalian α -crystallins also bear considerable sequence homology (Fig. 1). The sequence of α -crystallin can be broadly divided into three regions⁹: (a) N-terminal region containing residues ~1-60; (b) α -crystallin domain containing residues ~61-145; and (c) C-terminal extension containing residues 146-173 for human α A-crystallin or 146-175 for human α B-crystallin. A careful look into the sequences (Fig. 1) re-

veals that in the α -crystallin domain of nearly 80 residues, the sequence remains highly conserved³¹ among various sHSPs. Variations in the primary sequence are mainly in the N- and C-terminal domains.

Secondary structure : Although primary structures of α -crystallin from many species are known for quite some time, knowledge about the secondary and tertiary structures of α -crystallin is limited due to its large size and limited X-ray crystallographic data. Based on circular dichroism measurements the secondary structure is believed to be dominated by β -pleated sheet structure with very little α -helices³²⁻³⁵. Early study by Seizen and Agros³⁵ estimated approximately 50% β -sheet and 3% α -helix. These estimates were supported by FT-IR data³⁶. In fact all three α -, β - and γ -crystallin were found to have major β -sheet protein with small but varying amount of α -helix content³⁷.

Tertiary structure : Very little is known about the tertiary structure of α -crystallin. The information about the tertiary structure was primarily obtained by probing the environments of various amino acids or the location of hydrophobic sites³⁸. The tertiary structure of lens α -, β - and γ -crystallin was studied by absorption, fluorescence and near UV-CD spectroscopy³⁹⁻⁴². α -Crystallin showed age-related difference in tertiary structure⁴⁰⁻⁴². These studies showed that α -crystallin possessed a fairly buried tryptophan residue, with lots of exposed hydrophobic pockets. Some studies have reported the existence of 2-3 domains for α -crystallin in which each monomer is having a distinct N-terminal hydrophobic and C-terminal hydrophilic domain⁴³⁻⁴⁵.

Quaternary structure : The quaternary structure of α -crystallin has been the subject of much debate and speculation. α -Crystallin exists in solution as a polydisperse high molecular mass aggregate with a molecular weight distribution ranging from 300,000 to over 1 million Dalton. The models, proposed to describe the quaternary structure of α -crystallin, can be divided into three main groups : the three-layer models, the micelle-like models and the models of tetrameric building blocks^{43,46}. Other models such as rhombododecahedral structure⁴⁷, a two-layer structure composed of annuli of peptides⁴⁸ have also been proposed. A "pitted-flexiball" model suggested that tetrameric subunit building blocks were combined in an open mi-

Alpha-crystallin A-chain						50
Human	MDVTIQHPWF	KRTLGFYFYS	RLFDQFFGEG	LFEYDLLPFL	SSTISPYRQ	
Bovine	MDIAIQHPWF	KRTLGFYFYS	RLFDQFFGEG	LFEYDLLPFL	SSTISPYRQ	
Rabbit	MDVTIQHPWF	KRTLGFYFYS	RLFDQFFGEG	LFEYDLLPFL	SSTISPYRQ	
Rat	MDVTIQHPWF	KRALGFYFYS	RLFDQFFGEG	LFEYDLLPFL	SSTISPYRQ	
Mouse	MDVTIQHPWF	KRALGFYFYS	RLFDQFFGEG	LFEYDLLPFL	SSTISPYRQ	
Chicken	MDITIQHPWF	KRALGPLIPS	RLFDQFFGEG	LLEYDLLPLF	SSTISPYRQ	
	:*:***	**:*:***:	**	*****	*:*****:	*****
						100
Human	SLFRTVLDSG	ISE-----	-----	-----VRSD	RDKFVIFLDV	
Bovine	SLFRTVLDSG	ISE-----	-----	-----VRSD	RDKFVIFLDV	
Rabbit	SLFRTVLDSG	ISE-----	-----	-----VRSD	RDKFVIFLDV	
Rat	SLFRTVLDSG	ISELMTHMWF	VMHQPHAGNP	KNNPGKVRSD	RDKFVIFLDV	
Mouse	SLFRTVLDSG	ISELMTHMWF	VMHQPHAGNP	KNNPVKVRSD	RDKFVIFLDV	
Chicken	SLFRSVLESG	ISE-----	-----	-----VRSD	RDKFTIMLDV	
	:*:	***		****	****	*:***
						150
Human	KHFSPEDLTV	KVQDDFVEIH	GKHNERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPSNVDQS	
Bovine	KHFSPEDLTV	KVQEDFVEIH	GKHNERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPSNVDQS	
Rabbit	KHFSPEDLTV	KVQEDFVEIH	GKHNERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPSNVDQS	
Rat	KHFSPEDLTV	KVLEDFVEIH	GKHNERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPSNVDQS	
Mouse	KHFSPEDLTV	KVLEDFVEIH	GKHNERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPSNVDQS	
Chicken	KHFSPEDLSV	KIIDDFVEIH	GKHSERQDDH	GYISREFHRR	YRLPANVDQS	
	*****:*	*:*****	***.*****	*****	*****	*****
						196
Human	ALSCSLSADG	MLTFCGPKIQ	TGLDATHAER	AIPVSREEKP	TSAPSS	
Bovine	ALSCSLSADG	MLTFSGPKIP	SGVDAGHSER	AIPVSREEKP	SSAPSS	
Rabbit	ALSCSLSADG	MLTFSGPKVQ	SGLDAGHSER	AIPVSREEKP	SSVPSS	
Rat	ALSCSLSADG	MLTFSGPKVQ	SGLDAGHSER	AIPVSREEKP	SSAPSS	
Mouse	ALSCSLSADG	MLTFSGPKVQ	SGLDAGHSER	AIPVSREEKP	SSAPSS	
Chicken	AITCSLSSDG	MLTFSGPKVP	SNMDPSHSER	PIPVSREEKP	TSAPSS	
	*:*****	****.***:	:.:*. *:*	.*****	:*.***	
Alpha-crystallin B-chain						50
Human	MDIAIHHPWI	RRPFFPFHSP	SRLFDQFFGE	HLLESDFLPT	STSLSPFYLR	
Bovine	MDIAIHHPWI	RRPFFPFHSP	SRLFDQFFGE	HLLESDFLPA	STSLSPFYLR	
Rabbit	MDIAIHHPWI	RRPFFPFHSP	SRLFDQFFGE	HLLESDFLPT	STSLSPFYLR	
Rat	MDIAIHHPWI	RRPFFPFHSP	SRLFDQFFGE	HLLESDFLST	ATSLSPFYLR	
Mouse	MDIAIHHPWI	RRPFFPFHSP	SRLFDQFFGE	HLLESDFST	ATSLSPFYLR	
Chicken	MDITIHNPLI	RRPLFSWLTP	SRIFDQIFGE	HLQESELLPT	SPSLSPFLMR	
	:*:*	***:*:*	**:*:	** *:*:..	:.*****	*:
						100
Human	PPSFLRAPSW	FDTGLSEMRL	EKDRFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDVIEV	
Bovine	PPSFLRAPSW	IDTGLSEMRL	EKDRFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDVIEV	
Rabbit	PPSFLRAPSW	IDTGLSEMRL	EKDRFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDVIEV	
Rat	PPSFLRAPSW	IDTGLSEMRM	EKDRFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDVIEV	
Mouse	PPSFLRAPSW	IDTGLSEMRL	EKDRFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDVIEV	
Chicken	SP-FFRMP	LETGLSEMRL	EKDKFSVNLD	VKHFSPEELK	VKVLGDMIEI	
	. * *:*	::*****:	***:*****	*****	*****:	*:
						150
Human	HGKHEERQDE	HGFISREFHR	KYRIPADVDP	LTITSSLSSD	GVLTVNGPRK	
Bovine	HGKHEERQDE	HGFISREFHR	KYRIPADVDP	LAITSSLSSD	GVLTVNGPRK	
Rabbit	HGKHEERQDE	HGFISREFHR	KYRIPADVDP	LTITSSLSSD	GVLTVNGPRK	
Rat	HGKHEERQDE	HGFISREFHR	KYRIPADVDP	LTITSSLSSD	GVLTVNGPRK	
Mouse	HGKHEERQDE	HGFISREFHR	KYRIPADVDP	LTITSSLSSD	GVLTVNGPRK	
Chicken	HGKHEERQDE	HGFIAREFSR	KYRIPADVDP	LTITSSLSLD	GVLTVSAPRK	
	*****	***:*:***	*****	*:*****	*****	***
						175
Human	QVSGPERTIP	ITREEKPAVT	AAPKK			
Bovine	QASGPERTIP	ITREEKPAVT	AAPKK			
Rabbit	QAPGPERTIP	ITREEKPAVT	AAPKK			
Rat	QASGPERTIP	ITREEKPAVT	AAPKK			
Mouse	QVSGPERTIP	ITREEKPAVA	AAPKK			
Chicken	QSDVPERSIP	ITREEKPAIA	GSQRK			
	* *:*	*****:	:.:*			

Fig. 1. Primary amino acid sequence of α A- and α B-crystallin of 6 different species

celle-like arrangement⁴⁹. Due to the polydisperse nature, crystal structure of α -crystallin is not available. Recently, a few sHSPs have been studied by cryo-electron microscopy^{50,51}. By this technique, α B-crystallin was found to have a variable quaternary structure with a central cavity⁵². Even though cryo-electron microscopy of HSP 16.5 yielded regular and symmetric assemblies, no clear symmetry was obtained for α -crystallin or HSP 27. On the other hand, it was observed that there were variable assemblies of α -crystallin. Electron microscopic data revealed that α -crystallin consists of globular particles of diameter 14–18 nm⁷ and can have a torus-like structure⁵³.

1.3. Stability of α -crystallin

The stability of proteins is related to covalent or conformational changes and these changes occur due to denaturation by heat or chemical reagents. α -Crystallin is readily denatured by heat and denaturant like urea or guanidine hydrochloride (Gu-HCl).

Stability against heat : α -Crystallin was believed to have a very high thermal stability^{54,55}. Even upto 100°C, α A-crystallin remained soluble, although α B-crystallin precipitated out around 65°C^{56–58}. α -Crystallin underwent a conformational transition between approximately 38 and 50°C indicating an increase in exposure of hydrophobic sites. This tertiary structural change is irreversible⁵⁹. Infrared spectroscopy showed a thermal transition between 60 and 62°C together with a massive loss of native secondary structure⁶⁰. Both infrared and circular dichroism spectroscopy demonstrated the thermal transition⁶¹ of α -crystallin around 61°C. Even though there was a destruction in secondary structure with increase in temperature, secondary structure fully recovered after cooling to 25°C indicating that high thermal stability and reversibility of α -crystallin⁶². The recovery of secondary structure but irreversibility of tertiary structure of α -crystallin was shown by several workers^{54,63,64}. The secondary structure of α B-crystallin is more stable than that of α A-crystallin⁶⁴. There occurs also an irreversible temperature-induced quaternary structural change of α -crystallin^{60,64,66}. From the functional point of view, for maintaining the transparency of the eye lens, high stability of α -crystallin is necessary in absence of protein turnover.

Stability against denaturant : Quaternary, tertiary and secondary structures are all broken down at high concen-

tration of denaturant like urea (non-ionic) and guanidine hydrochloride (ionic). The final state, possibly a random coil or fully extended polypeptide is often called an unfolded state. Experimental measurements of stability by various techniques often reflect different things. For example, fluorescence emission spectra revealed that 1 M Gu-HCl was required for 50% unfolding of bovine α -crystallin^{61,67}. On the other hand, far-UV CD measurements indicated that α -crystallin was 50% unfolded at approximately 1.5 M Gu-HCl⁶¹ or 2.6 M Gu-HCl⁶⁷. This is due to the fact that fluorescence emission spectra only reflect the unfolding of N-terminal region, since α A-crystallin contains only a single Trp (at position 9) and α B-crystallin contains two (at positions 9 and 60). In case of denaturation with urea, fluorescence spectroscopy showed 50% unfolding at about 2.9 M urea^{67,68} whereas it was 3.2 M in case of far-UV CD spectroscopy⁶⁷. The stabilities of α A- and α B-crystallin were quite different. In case of bovine α A-crystallin about 3 M urea required for 50% unfolding, while α B-crystallin was 50% unfolded at about 1 M urea⁶⁸. In Gu-HCl, the ΔG for human α A-crystallin was reported to be around 27 kJ/mol and 21 kJ/mol for α B-crystallin^{12,69}. Abgar *et al.*⁶⁹ reported the high stability for α A-crystallin at the level of tertiary and quaternary structure, although α B-crystallin is somewhat more stable than α A-crystallin at the level of secondary structure⁶³. From these data, it is clear that, α A-crystallin is more stable than α B-crystallin and α B-crystallin is stabilized when it is complexed with α A-crystallin in the α -crystallin assembly⁵⁷. The rapid refolding from 8 M urea showed that the refolded α -crystallin has native-like secondary, tertiary and quaternary structure⁷⁰. Although the structural change of α -crystallin against denaturant has been studied extensively, the role of this structural stability on the chaperone activity of α -crystallin still remains unknown.

1.4. Molecular chaperone function of α -crystallin

For a very long time α -crystallin was believed to be a structural protein with no apparent function attributed to it. One of the most important developments in α -crystallin research took place in 1992 when Horwitz⁷¹ reported for the first time that crystallin possessed molecular chaperone-like function. He showed that α -crystallin was able to prevent the heat induced aggregation of a number of

substrate proteins including β - and γ -crystallin⁷². He proposed that aggregation prevention could be its physiological function of α -crystallin and such a role is crucial to the maintenance of transparency of the lens *in vivo*. The results were quickly verified by various laboratories^{59,66,73–75} and it was revealed that α -crystallin not only prevented thermal aggregation of proteins, but could also prevent protein aggregation induced by disulphide bond cleavage⁷⁵ and UV-light exposure⁶⁶. The observation was extended to other sHSPs as well and it was concluded that all sHSPs are molecular chaperones⁷⁶. These observations suggested that α -crystallin plays a dual role in the lens : (i) as a major constituent of refractive medium of the lens and (ii) as a molecular chaperone protecting other lens proteins from aggregation. These findings triggered renewed interest in the α -crystallin research particularly in understanding the chaperone behavior and mechanism of chaperone action of α -crystallin.

The purpose of this review is not to present a comprehensive account of the huge literature present on the molecular chaperone function of α -crystallin, but to present an overview of the work done by our group in this specific area.

2. Characteristics of chaperone function of α -crystallin

2.1. Chaperone activity and micellar architecture

The structural features of a protein that makes it a chaperone are poorly understood⁷⁷. The chaperone α -crystallin exists as a large oligomer of average 40 subunits per unit. The exact arrangement of the subunits is not known. The oligomer is heterogeneous in size and because of this it has not been possible to crystallize the oligomer. In absence of high resolution X-ray crystallographic data, researchers have tried to model the subunit association structure in α -crystallin^{55,78–81}. All these models are based on micellar type architecture. We were interested to find out whether such a micellar structure was related to its chaperone function. We compared the known structures of other chaperones⁷⁷. To our surprise we found that most other chaperones had micellar type association. The best known among them was the X-ray structure of chaperonin GroEL⁸². It had 14 subunits arranged in two rings which are joined back to back creating a cylindrical hole at the centre. A very similar architecture was also found in the chaperone TriC which had nine subunits arranged in one ring^{83,84}. Thermosome is

another chaperone which has GroEL like micellar architecture^{85,86}. In fact a host of other chaperones have micelle-type architecture as has been reviewed by us⁷⁷. Most of these chaperones have domains containing bundles of hydrophobic residues located at the surface to interact with the substrate proteins or hydrophobic probes such as bis-ANS. Another characteristic of most of these chaperones is that they have a flexible tail containing charged residues^{77,87,88}. These hydrophobic domains and the hydrophilic tail are well separated. This is comparable to the general structure of micelle forming surfactants^{77,89}. All these led us to hypothesize that micelle-like association of proteins may be linked to its chaperone function⁷⁷.

We found at least two proteins namely, dimeric tubulin⁸⁷ and α _s-casein⁸⁸, not known as chaperone till then, which fulfilled similar criteria. We tested their chaperone-like activity and found that both proteins could effectively prevent protein aggregation^{87,88}. For example, α -crystallin depleted soluble protein from bovine eye lens contains primarily a mixture of β - and γ -crystallin which is prone to aggregation when heated at 60°C (Fig. 2). As could be seen from the Fig. 2 that tubulin could effectively prevent this thermal aggregation⁸⁷. It may be interesting to mention here that the chaperone activity of tu-

Fig. 2. Prevention of aggregation of α -crystallin-depleted soluble lens proteins by tubulin. Aggregation of total soluble fraction of bovine eye lens proteins at 60°C after the removal of α -crystallin was done under the following conditions : total volume of assay mixture, 1.0 ml; curve 1, 0.3 mg of α -crystallin-depleted soluble eye lens protein; curve 2, plus 0.03 mg of tubulin; curve 3, plus 0.04 mg of tubulin; curve 4, plus 0.06 mg of tubulin (This research was originally published in *J Biol. Chem.*, 1998, 273, 30077. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. (Ref. 87)).

bulin disappears if its flexible tail is cleaved⁸⁷. Similarly α_s -casein was found to prevent the thermal aggregation of whey protein and BSA⁸⁸ at 70°C (Fig. 3). The observation of the chaperone behavior of tubulin has significance in understanding protein folding in eukaryotic cytosol where the abundance of other chaperones is quite low⁸⁷.

Fig. 3. Prevention of thermal aggregation of whey proteins by α_s -casein. (A) Aggregation assay of whey protein isolate (0.5 mg/ml, 10 mM phosphate buffer, pH 6.6, temperature 70°C). Curve 1, only whey protein isolate; curve 2, plus 0.4 mg/ml α_s -casein. (B) Aggregation assay of bovine serum albumin (0.5 mg/ml, 10 mM phosphate buffer, pH 6.6, temperature 70°C). Curve 1, only bovine serum albumin; curve 2, plus 0.5 mg/ml α_s -casein (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1999, 274, 15505. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. (Ref. 88)).

On the other hand the chaperone behavior of the intrinsically unstructured protein α_s -casein provides vital clue to protein folding machinery at the very early stages of evolution of life⁸⁸. The discovery of two new chaperones strengthens the micellar connection to chaperone function. Based on our hypothesis other researcher had also reported new chaperone⁹⁰.

2.2. Temperature and chaperone activity

Chaperone activity assay is often done at an elevated temperature measuring thermal aggregation of proteins.

However in the “insulin assay” the aggregation of insulin B chain is triggered by cleaving the disulphide bond linking the chain A with B and hence can be carried out at room temperature⁷⁵. Similarly the UV-light induced aggregation can also be carried out at room temperature⁶⁶. It has been usually found that room temperature assays normally required higher ratio of chaperone over the substrate to inhibit the aggregation completely. For example, insulin required at least 6 fold α -crystallin (insulin : α -crystallin 1 : 6) to completely prevent the aggregation of its B chain at room temperature⁷⁵, but at 1 : 1 ratio α -crystallin could nearly completely prevent aggregation of rhodanese⁹¹ at 47°C. These results showed that chaperone activity may be linked to temperature. Raman *et al.*⁹² claimed that chaperone activity of α -crystallin is triggered by a thermal switch. They reported that below 30°C, α -crystallin is not active as a chaperone. It activated only above 30°C. By this time a lot of chaperone data of α -crystallin was available in the literature. Data from our laboratory showed considerable chaperone activity of α -crystallin at room temperature. We undertook a thorough study of the temperature-chaperone activity relationship⁹³. Using insulin as the substrate we carried out chaperone assay between the temperature range 18–37°C. At a given α -crystallin concentration the chaperone activity measured by the percentage protection of aggregation of insulin B chain were temperature dependent. The chaperone activity increased with increase of temperature, but even at the temperature of 18°C it showed considerable chaperone activity⁹³ (Table 1A). It only required higher amount of α -crystallin to prevent this aggregation completely (Table 1B). Thus contrary to Raman *et al.*⁹² our findings clearly showed that α -crystallin is not inactive below 30°C as reported and does not require a thermal activation to switch to active form. Lens is a thermally insulated organ. The concept of thermal activation of chaperone activity of lens protein α -crystallin above 30°C is not physiologically relevant. α -Crystallin is present in the lenses of cold blooded animals also. A large number of vertebrates residing in cold weather conditions would be deprived of the chaperone function if such activation switch for α -crystallin existed⁹³. The rise of chaperone activity can be easily linked to exposure of hydrophobic groups on the surface of α -crystallin as has been reported by us⁵⁹ and explained in the later section.

Table 1A. Temperature dependent prevention of aggregation of insulin by α -crystallin at 1 : 1 (w/w) ratio

Temperature (°C)	Percentage protection*
18	26 ± 0.32
23	28 ± 0.13
27	28 ± 0.51
37	52 ± 0.83

Table 1B. Dose dependent prevention of aggregation of insulin by α -crystallin at 18°C

Ratio of insulin : α -crystallin	Percentage protection*
1 : 1	26 ± 0.32
1 : 6	74 ± 0.11
1 : 12	95 ± 0.23

*Percentage protection is calculated using the equation $(I_0 - I_\infty)/I_0 \times 100$; where I_0 is the light scattering in the absence and I_∞ in the presence of α -crystallin at a fixed time (30 min) after initiation of the reaction with DTT.

2.3. Oligomeric size and chaperone activity of α -crystallin

One of the most striking features of the structure of α -crystallin is its oligomeric association⁷⁸⁻⁸². As discussed earlier, this feature is common among many other known chaperones⁷⁷. Based on these observations many workers have proposed that oligomerization is a prerequisite for chaperone function^{46,94,95}. We undertook a study to examine the relationship between oligomeric size and chaperone activity of recombinant α A- and α B-crystallin⁹⁶. We used tryptic digestion as tool to digest the α -crystallin sequence and thus affect its oligomeric size and measured its oligomeric size and chaperone activity. We digested α A- and α B-crystallin under controlled condition for various length of time. We were able to identify bands of α -crystallin ranging from 12 to 20 kDa on SDS PAGE (Fig. 4). The oligomeric size of the resultant oligomers were compared by three different methods namely gel filtration chromatography, membrane filtration method and light scattering technique⁹⁶. Gel filtration revealed only two types of oligomer one around 500 kDa and others are below 20 kDa (Fig. 5A). No other size could be identified. Through membrane filtration the oligomers were divided into two categories above and below 100 kDa. The relative population of the two categories changed with time (Fig. 5B). Scattering measured by 90° scattering in a fluorimeter using same wavelength as both excitation and emission also showed a general decrease in oligomeric size with increase in digestion time (Fig. 5C).

Fig. 4. SDS-PAGE of α A-crystallin (panel A) and α B-crystallin (panel B) digested with trypsin for various intervals of time. Panel A : lane 1, 0 min; lane 2, 15 min; lane 3, 30 min; lane 4, 45 min; lane 5, 1 h; lane 6, 1.5 h; lane 7, 2 h; lane 8, 3 h. Panel B : lane 1, 0 min; lane 2, 15 min; lane 3, 30 min; lane 4, 1 h; lane 5, 2 h; lane 6, 3 h; lane 7, 5 h; lane 8, 8 h (This research was originally published in *Proteins*, 2004, 57, 610. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. (Ref. 96)).

Fig. 5. Determination of oligomeric size of recombinant α A- and α B-crystallin with the progress of tryptic digestion by various methods. (A) Gel filtration profile of digested α A-crystallin as a function of digestion time : trace 1, 30 min; trace 2, 1 h; trace 3, 2 h; trace 4, 6 h (B) Centrifugal filtration through 100 kDa membrane. Percentage of α A- and α B-crystallin passing through the membrane is shown as a function of digestion time. (C) Ninety-degree light scattering as measured in a fluorimeter of α A- and α B-crystallin solution as a function of digestion time. Scattering was measured at 37°C using 400 nm as the excitation and emission wavelengths, using 0.2 mg/mL protein solution (plus trypsin; α -crystallin : trypsin ratio of 100 : 1 by wt) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 (This research was originally published in *Proteins*, 2004, 57, 610. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. (Ref. 96)).

Chaperone activity of the partially digested α -crystallin was measured by insulin assay. It was found that initial digestion for up to 60 min increased chaperone activity although the oligomeric size decreased (Fig. 6). But chaperone activity decreased from 85% to 40% as digestion time increased from 1.5 to 2 h. Interestingly α A-crystallin

Fig. 6. Insulin aggregation assay of chaperone activity of digested α A- and α B-crystallin at 25°C. Assay mixture (600 μ l) contained insulin (0.35 mg/ml), digested α A-crystallin (1.05 mg/ml) or digested α B-crystallin (0.35 mg/ml) and 20 mM DTT in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. Panel A : α A-crystallin digested for different time. Trace 1, 0 min; trace 2, 15 min; trace 3, 1 h; trace 4, 2 h; trace 5, 8 h. Panel B : α B-crystallin digested for different time. Trace 1, 0 min; trace 2, 15 min; trace 3, 1 h; trace 4, 2 h; trace 5, 3 h; trace 6, 5 h; trace 7, no α -crystallin (control). The control for panel A and B were same (This research was originally published in *Proteins*, 2004, 57, 610. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. (Ref. 96)).

retained 65% activity even when 70% of α B-crystallin was below 100 kDa. Thus the chaperone activity of tryptic digest of α -crystallin did not directly correlated with the loss of oligomeric size. Although these results do not support the accepted notion, results in support of our observation are prevalent in the literature^{49,97-99}. For example, it has been reported that enlargement of oligomeric size resulted no change in chaperone activity^{49,98}. Others reported complete loss of chaperone activity on increase in oligomeric size of α -crystallin⁹⁷⁻⁹⁹. In fact a 19 residue peptide from the α -crystallin domain of human α A-crystallin has been reported to have significant activity¹⁰⁰. We concluded that chaperone activity has no direct correlation with oligomeric size. Our results showed that exposed surface hydrophobicity of tryptic digested α -crystallin close correlated with its chaperone function⁹⁶.

2.4. α -Crystallin assisted refolding of enzyme substrates

α -Crystallin is known to prevent thermal aggregation proteins. It also prevents protein aggregation induced by

disulphide bond cleavage^{59,75} or UV-light. α -Crystallin has also been implicated under specific experimental conditions in the *in vitro* refolding of many enzyme substrates although the relevance of such activity has been questioned^{66,101-106}. We reported that GroEL was effective in preventing aggregation both in the unfolding and refolding pathway⁹¹, but α -crystallin was effective only in the unfolding pathway. However, conditions can be created, particularly in the very low substrate concentration when significant enzyme refolding in presence of α -crystallin was possible¹⁰⁷. About 25% yield of refolded enzyme in presence of α -crystallin was reported by many workers¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁴. We standardized the conditions to maximize the yield of α -crystallin assisted refolding of enzymes¹⁰⁷. We found that when refolding of enzymes were attempted in presence of bovine α L-crystallin about 25% yield of active enzymes were obtained (Fig. 7). However when the refolding was carried out in presence of recom-

Fig. 7. Influence of bovine α L-crystallin on the reactivation of different substrate enzymes. (A) Time course of reactivation of MDH (10 nM) in presence of 30 μ M bovine α L-crystallin (trace 2), 30 μ M BSA (trace 3) and in absence of α L-crystallin (trace 1). (B) Time course of reactivation of CA (50 nM) in presence of 30 μ M bovine α L-crystallin (trace 2), 30 μ M BSA (trace 3) and in absence of α L-crystallin (trace 1). (C) Time course of reactivation of LDH (10 nM) in presence of 30 μ M bovine α L-crystallin (trace 2), 30 μ M BSA (trace 3) and in absence of α L-crystallin (trace 1) (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, 26, 247. © Springer, Netherlands. (Ref. 107)).

binant α B-crystallin under the same conditions described under Fig. 7, over 40% yield could be achieved (Table 2). Our results showed enhancement of refolding yield in presence of osmolytes such as sucrose and glycerol. Even

Table 2. Reactivation yield of different denatured enzymes in absence and presence of BSA, α A- and α B-crystallin

Reactivation of enzyme from 6 (M) Gu.HCl	Added component	Reactivation yield (%)
Malate dehydrogenase (MDH)	None	4.7
	30 μ M α A-crystallin	28.0
	30 μ M α B-crystallin	41.0
	30 μ M BSA	5.1
Carbonic anhydrase (CA)	None	2.3
	30 μ M α A-crystallin	29.0
	30 μ M α B-crystallin	37.0
	30 μ M BSA	2.9
Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)	None	5.2
	30 μ M α A-crystallin	23.0
	30 μ M α B-crystallin	42.0
	30 μ M BSA	5.9

the presence of 3 mM ATP could significantly enhance the activity yield of malate dehydrogenase (MDH) to nearly 50% when chaperoned by α B-crystallin¹⁰⁷ (Fig. 8). Interestingly ATP hydrolysis was not required for the

Fig. 8. Time course of reactivation of LDH at 37°C from 6 M Gu-HCl solution in presence of 3 mM different nucleotides. 1, 10 nM LDH alone; 2, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin; 3, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM AMP; 4, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM ADP; 5, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM ATP- γ -S; 6, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM ATP. Refolding was initiated by 100-fold dilution of LDH (1 μ M) in 6 M Gu-HCl in a refolding buffer (50 mM phosphate, pH 7.5) containing 10 mM Mg-acetate and 5 mM DTT (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, 26, 247. © Springer, Netherlands. (Ref. 107)).

folding process as use of ATP- γ S, a non-hydrolysable analogue of ATP made very little difference in refolding yield¹⁰⁷ (Fig. 8).

It may be worthwhile to mention here that α -crystallin himself could easily refold from unfolded state¹⁰⁸. We made a detailed study of the refolding behavior of α -crystallin from its fully unfolded state in 6 M GuHCl. We used various methods such circular dichroism, fluorescence, light scattering, and fluorescence polarization to compare the secondary, tertiary and quaternary structure of native and refolded α -crystallin. We found that the secondary structure as monitored by the ellipticity of α -crystallin during unfolding and refolding was fully reversible (Fig. 9). But the tertiary and quaternary structures of the refolded α -crystallin were slightly different from that of the native state. In Fig. 10 we show the bis-ANS titration data of native and refolded α -crystallin. The refolded form has higher exposed hydrophobicity than the native α -crystallin. The refolded form had lower oligomeric size and higher chaperone activity¹⁰⁸.

2.5. Role of N-terminal in the chaperone function of α -crystallin

As we have seen in the primary sequences that the N- and C-terminal parts of the sequence of α -crystallin from different species vary appreciably in length as well as amino acid sequence while the central α -crystallin do-

Fig. 9. Unfolding and refolding profiles of α_L -crystallin observed by circular dichroic measurement. Ellipticity (θ) at 222 nm for unfolding (solid square) and refolding (open circle) of α_L -crystallin was plotted against urea concentration. Concentration of α_L -crystallin was 0.5 mg/mL in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, 26, 315. © Springer, Netherlands. (Ref. 108)).

Fig. 10. Binding of bis-ANS by native and urea unfolded α_L -crystallin. Fluorescence intensity at 480 nm was measured as a function of bis-ANS concentration taking excitation wavelength as 390 nm for native (solid circle) and urea unfolded (solid square) α_L -crystallin. α_L -Crystallin concentration was 0.1 mg/mL (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, 26, 315. © Springer, Netherlands. (Ref. 108)).

main remain largely conserved^{9,31,109}. While the conserved domain has been linked to its function, the role of the terminal domains in the physical properties of α -crystallin remained unknown. N-terminal domain has been thought to be the substrate binding site¹¹⁰, but whether different substrates bind to different sites were unknown⁹. In order to understand the role of the N-terminal region for its structure, function and stability we did site directed truncation to systematically raise various N-terminal deletion mutant of αA -crystallin¹¹¹ (Fig. 11). We determined the oligomeric status of the various deletion

Fig. 11. Schematic presentation of N-terminal truncated mutants (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2007, 86, 315. © Wiley Periodicals Inc. (Ref. 111)).

mutant of α -crystallin by FPLC gel filtration in a Superose 12 column precalibrated with known molecular mass standards. The molecular weights of the oligomers are reported in Table 3. It shows that the molecular mass of full length α -crystallin oligomer was ~ 500 kDa which decreased by 5–7% on deletion of up to first 20 residues from the N-terminal. Further deletion led to drastic decrease in size to ~ 50 kDa. The number of subunits in the oligomer drastically reduced to 4 from ~ 25 on deleting more than 20 residues from the N-terminal¹¹¹ (Table 3).

Table 3. Molecular weights of wild type human αA -crystallin and N-terminal mutants obtained from FPLC gel filtration profile

N-terminal deletion mutants	Approx. molecular weight (kDa)	Molecular weight of oligomers (kDa)	Number of subunits
Wild type (1-173)	20	500	25
N Δ 10 (10-173)	19	470	~ 25
N Δ 20 (20-173)	18	465	~ 26
N Δ 24 (24-173)	17.5	444	~ 26
N Δ 35 (35-173)	15.7	363	~ 23
		308	~ 19
N Δ 40 (40-173)	15	151	~ 10
N Δ 50 (50-173)	14	55	~ 4
		92	~ 7
N Δ 62 (62-173)	13	56	~ 4

The secondary structure of the deleted α -crystallin was measured by CD spectroscopy. Deletion of 10 and residues from the N-terminal did not change shape of the CD spectra although negative ellipticity decreased (Fig. 12). But loss of α -sheet structure was evident when more than 20 residues are deleted¹¹¹. The chaperone activity measured by percentage protection against thermal aggregation of its substrate β -crystallin follow similar trend. Thus 94% protection was obtained when up to 20 residues were deleted, but decreased to 60% when 35 residues were deleted. The chaperone activity nearly disappeared when 50 or more residues were deleted. Interestingly when a non-natural substrate carbonic anhydrase (CA) was used the deletion of first 10 residues resulted in 50% loss of activity clearly showing that different substrates responded differently towards chaperone function of deleted αA -crystallin mutants¹¹¹.

The stability of the deletion mutants were determined by equilibrium unfolding method using urea as the denaturant and monitoring the near UV circular dichroic spectra

Fig. 12. Circular dichroic measurements of the wild type and mutant α A-crystallin. (A) Far UV circular dichroism spectra of human α A-crystallin and N-terminal mutants. Proteins were (0.5 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer of pH 7.5 at 25°C. Spectra were recorded in 250–200 nm region; 1, wild type; 2, N Δ 10; 3, N Δ 20; 4, N Δ 50; 5, N Δ 62. (B) Near UV circular dichroism spectra of human α A-crystallin and N-terminal mutants (1 mg/ml). Spectra were recorded in 350–250 nm region; 1, wild type; 2, N Δ 10; 3, N Δ 20; 4, N Δ 50; 5, N Δ 62 (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2007, 86, 177. © Wiley Periodicals Inc. (Ref. 111)).

at different urea concentration. The unfolding profiles were analyzed by both a two state as well as a three state model^{111,112}. According to two and three state model

$$F(U) = \frac{I_0 + I \exp(-\Delta G^0 + m[U]/RT)}{I + \exp(-\Delta G^0 + m[U]/RT)} \quad (1)$$

$$F(U) = \frac{I_0 + I_1 \exp(-\Delta G^0_{NI} + m_{NI}[U]/RT) + I_\infty \exp(-\Delta G^0_{IU} + m_{IU}[U]/RT)}{I + \exp(-\Delta G^0_{NI} + m_{NI}[U]/RT) + \exp(-\Delta G^0_{IU} + m_{IU}[U]/RT)} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (1) and eq. (2) were used to calculate the thermodynamic stability of the deletion mutant in terms of free energy change ΔG^0 for unfolding from native state. The ΔG^0 values are shown in Table 4. The results showed that N-terminal residues are important to maintain stability of the proteins as deletion of these residues drastically effected stability. Therefore it became evident that

Table 4. Parameters of equilibrium urea unfolding of N-terminal mutants of human α A-crystallin at 25°C, obtained from the two state model $N \leftrightarrow U$ and three state model $N \leftrightarrow I \leftrightarrow U$ fit

N-terminal deletion mutant	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol) (According to <i>three</i> <i>state model</i>)	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol) (According to <i>two</i> <i>state model</i>)
Wild type (1-173)	27.0 \pm 0.7	12.1 \pm 0.41
N Δ 10 (10-173)	20.0 \pm 1.8	9.5 \pm 0.52
N Δ 20 (20-173)	16.8 \pm 1.6	8.1 \pm 0.40
N Δ 24 (24-173)	16.0 \pm 1.2	7.5 \pm 0.21
N Δ 35 (35-173)	14.1 \pm 6.4	5.7 \pm 0.18
N Δ 50 (50-173)	10.6 *	0.78 \pm 0.10
N Δ 62 (62-173)	Not fitted by <i>three</i> <i>state model</i>	Not fitted by <i>two</i> <i>state model</i>

N-terminal residues not only control the oligomeric size of the α -crystallin, it is crucial for its stability. This domain not only provides regions for inter-subunit contacts, it also accommodates substrate contacts. Loss of chaperone activity due to deletion of N-terminal residues is partly due to loss of solubility of the deletion mutant. There is also reduction in subunit exchange rates on deletion of N-terminal residues. But the most important role of the N-terminal region of α -crystallin is to provide extra thermodynamic stability to the chaperone molecule through oligomerization¹¹¹.

3. Substrate recognition by α -crystallin

3.1. Recognition of hydrophobic patches by α -crystallin

The mechanism of interception of the substrate protein by the chaperone α -crystallin drew considerable interest of scientists. In the case of classical chaperone GroEL from *E. coli* a large number of studies suggested that initial recognition took place through exposed hydrophobic patches on the surface of the chaperone and the substrate^{113–118}. For α -crystallin also Raman and Rao⁶⁶ suggested a similar mechanism. These suggestions suffer from complication because of the fact that chaperone activity of α -crystallin was assayed at an elevated temperatures between 45–65°C^{71,74,97} and the conformational transitions and particularly exposure of hydrophobic patches varied with temperature. Raman and Rao⁶⁶ reported from pyrene fluorescence measurements as a function of temperature that several structural transition takes place in α -crystallin above 30°C that correlated with chaperone activity of α -crystallin.

In order to understand how exposure of surface hydrophobicity changed with temperature, we added to α -

crystallin the conformation sensitive hydrophobic probe bis-ANS and measured its fluorescence intensity changes as a function of temperature⁵⁹ (Fig. 13). Our results show an initial decrease intensity as temperature increased from 25°C up to 37°C. This decrease was interpreted as due to thermal deactivation of the fluorophore. From 37°C to 50°C there was a rise in intensity reflecting increased exposure of hydrophobic sites on the chaperone surface. Above 52°C the intensity decreased steadily. Interestingly when the temperature was gradually decreased from 60°C, the emission intensity was not reversible and went higher than that in the heating cycle (Fig. 13). The conformation that α -crystallin adopted on cooling after heat treatment was characterized by significantly enhanced surface hydrophobicity⁵⁹.

Fig. 13. Temperature dependence of fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) of bis-ANS (13 μ M) in presence of α -crystallin (0.06 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. (•) First heating cycle; (×) First cooling cycle; (□) Second heating cycle (This research was originally published in *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, 369, 321. © Elsevier. (Ref. 59)).

The above results gave us an opportunity to test the relationship between surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity of α -crystallin by varying exposed surface hydrophobicity but performing the chaperone assay at a constant temperature employing insulin aggregation assay. Surface hydrophobicity of α -crystallin was varied by preincubating the solution at different temperature and cooling back to 22°C. The results show clear correlation between preincubation temperature and exposed surface hydrophobicity in the temperature range 40–60°C (Fig. 14). The results shown in Fig. 15 clearly demonstrate that the α -crystallin preincubated at higher temperature is more efficient in preventing insulin aggregation reveal-

Fig. 14. Fluorescence emission intensity at 22°C of bis-ANS (13 μ M) in presence of α -crystallin as a function of preincubation temperature. Samples of α -crystallin (0.05 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2) were preincubated at different temperature for 15 min and cooled down to room temperature. bis-ANS (13 μ M final concentration) was then added and fluorescence emission intensity was measured at 490 nm at room temperature (This research was originally published in *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, 369, 321. © Elsevier. (Ref. 59)).

Fig. 15. DTT induced aggregation of insulin B chain at 22°C in absence and presence of α -crystallin (0.125 mg/ml) preincubated at different temperature. (A) No α -crystallin; (B) α -crystallin preincubated at 22°C; (C) α -crystallin preincubated at 50°C; (D) α -crystallin preincubated at 60°C (This research was originally published in *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, 369, 321. © Elsevier. (Ref. 59)).

ing positive correlation between surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity of α -crystallin. Surface hydrophobicity can be modulated not only by thermal means but by other factors as well (for example, by some bivalent metal ions^{119,120} as discussed later). We conclude

that hydrophobicity chaperone activity correlation may constitute an integral part of the mechanism of recognition of substrate protein by chaperone α -crystallin not only by lens protein α -crystallin but by HSP in general.

3.2. Substrate specificity of α -crystallin

Chaperone function is general property of various classes of HSP's¹²¹⁻¹²⁴. However whether all the chaperones have similar substrate specificity is unclear. The most widely studied chaperone function is that of *E. coli* chaperonin GroEL which bind unfolded or partly unfolded substrate proteins. To compare the substrate specificity of α -crystallin with GroEL we chose a common substrate rhodanese as the folding intermediates of rhodanese were well characterized. It has been already demonstrated that GroEL could prevent aggregation of rhodanese both during refolding from fully unfolded forms in strongly denaturant solution¹²⁵ as well as during unfolding by heat treatment¹²⁶. We studied the prevention of thermal aggregation of rhodanese at 47°C (Fig. 16). We found that at approximately 1 : 1 molar ratio between α -crystallin and rhodanese, the aggregation could be almost completely prevented⁹¹. This confirmed that α -crystallin recognized intermediates of rhodanese in its unfolding pathway. These results were quite similar to that of GroEL and other heat shock proteins^{23,25,46,71,72}.

Fig. 16. Thermal aggregation of rhodanese at 47°C (A) and its suppression by 0.045 μ M α -crystallin (1.8 μ M on the monomer basis) (B) and 0.135 μ M α -crystallin (5.4 μ M on the monomer basis) (C) (This research was originally published in *Biochem. J.*, 1995, 311, 367. © Portland Press Limited (Ref. 91)).

We then proceeded to study the prevention of aggregation of rhodanese in its refolding condition from a fully unfolded state. We injected fully unfolded rhodanese from 6 M guanidine hydrochloride solution in to α -crystallin solution. The results shown in Fig. 17 reveal that α -crystallin failed to suppress this aggregation even when the concentration of oligomeric α -crystallin was three times the molar concentration of rhodanese. Repetition of the

Fig. 17. Aggregation of rhodanese during refolding from 6 M guanidinium chloride in the absence (a) and presence of α -crystallin at a concentration (oligomer) of 0.21 μ M (b), 0.42 μ M (c) and 0.71 μ M (d) (This research was originally published in *Biochem. J.*, 1995, 311, 367. © Portland Press Limited (Ref. 91)).

same experiment with GroEL in our laboratory showed that GroEL at equimolar concentration fully prevented such aggregation of rhodanese. Even when rhodanese was replaced by substrates β - or γ -crystallin, α -crystallin was unable to prevent aggregation in the refolding pathway. For all three substrates our data showed that native α -crystallin was unable to bind to folding intermediates formed during the refolding process. Thus while GroEL is able to recognize intermediates of substrates both in the unfolding and refolding pathway, the specificity of α -crystallin is limited to conformational intermediates that occur in the unfolding pathway only⁹¹.

This difference in specificity may be linked to their functioning under physiological conditions. Chaperone such GroEL are an integral part of protein folding ma-

chinery *in vitro* and is present in all cell types. On the contrary the presence of α -crystallin is restricted to specific tissues and unlikely to be part of the general folding machinery. Its primary role is to bind aggregation prone non-native conformer that may be formed in response to various stress conditions. This specificity of α -crystallin appears to be uniquely suited for its role in maintaining the transparency of the high density protein mass in eye lens.

3.3. Tertiary structure of recognized substrate by α -crystallin

Specific conformational states of non-native proteins recognized by classical molecular chaperones have drawn considerable attention of scientists^{127,128}. Some chaperones such as DnaK and PapD bind polypeptides in an extended conformation while some other chaperones such as GroEL and DnaJ prefer to bind to molten globule like conformers having highly flexible tertiary structure but largely preserved secondary structure¹²⁹⁻¹³². In order to get insight on what conformers of aggregation prone intermediates are recognized by α -crystallin, it is important to know about the tertiary structure of the chaperone bound client proteins. Tryptophan fluorescence maximum is a useful indicator of the tertiary structure of proteins¹³³. In the native state the tryptophan fluorescence maximum lies in the range 330-337 nm but in the fully extended state the maximum shifts to above 350 nm. To get the information regarding the tertiary structure of the protein bound to α -crystallin we used the recombinant α A-crystallin which has a single tryptophan residue at position 9. Employing site directed mutagenesis this tryptophan was replaced by the residue phenylalanine¹³⁴ (W9F). The complex formed between substrate protein and the W9F mutant of α -crystallin was used for fluorescence spectroscopy. Under this condition the tryptophan spectrum provides information for the substrate protein only. We compared the tryptophan spectrum of the bound substrate with those at native and fully extended conformation. The results for two substrates namely rhodanese and α -crystallin are shown in Fig. 18.

The fluorescence spectrum of native rhodanese has a maximum at 332 nm (Fig. 18A, trace 1) is consistent with a largely apolar environment of its Trp residues. Upon unfolding in 6 M guanidine HCl, the fluorescence maximum of rhodanese shifted to 352 nm, a wavelength characteristic of tryptophans fully exposed to water. Com-

Fig. 18. Fluorescence emission spectra of rhodanese (A) and γ -crystallin (B). 1, native protein; 2, protein bound to W9F α A-crystallin; 3, protein unfolded in 6 M guanidine HCl. Spectra were recorded at 25°C (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1996, 271, 10449. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. (Ref. 134)).

pared to these, the spectrum of rhodanese bound to W9F α A-crystallin has a maximum at 337 nm (Fig. 18A, trace 2). The 5 nm red-shift in the emission maximum indicates that the tertiary structure of the chaperone-bound enzyme is somewhat compromised compared to that in the native state; however, the average environment of Trp residues in the bound protein appeared to be still fairly hydrophobic. Thus the tertiary structure of bound rhodanese appeared to be closer to that of the native conformation than the fully extended state¹³⁴.

The fluorescence properties of α -crystallin bound to α A-crystallin were very similar to those of rhodanese. γ -Crystallin containing four Trp residues resulted in a 23 nm red-shift of the emission maximum in complete unfolding (from 330 nm in the native form to 353 nm). The bound γ -crystallin caused a red-shift of only 7 nm from that of its native state suggesting that the chaperone bound protein is characterized by a relatively low degree of unfolding¹³⁴.

Tertiary structure of α -crystallin bound substrate proteins was also probed by tryptophan fluorescence quenching experiments using acrylamide and iodide as a complementary set of water-soluble quenchers. Acrylamide has the ability to penetrate into protein interiors but the quench-

ing ability of negatively charged iodide is limited almost exclusively to surface-exposed tryptophans¹³³. Fig. 19 shows representative Stern-Volmer plots for the quenching of Trp fluorescence of rhodanese and γ -crystallin in the native, chaperone bound and fully unfolded states. Unfolding of both rhodanese and γ -crystallin in 6 M guanidine HCl at 25°C resulted in a greatly increased solvent exposure of Trp residues, as revealed by 6-fold increase in $(K_{SV})_{eff}$ (initial slope of the lines) for acrylamide in contrast to only a 2-fold increase of the above parameter observed for the proteins bound to W9F mutant of α A-

Fig. 19. Stern-Volmer plots for the quenching of the fluorescence of rhodanese (A) and γ -crystallin (B). *Top panel* for each protein represents iodide quenching, and the *bottom panel* represents acrylamide quenching. (*) native protein; (+) protein unfolded in 6 M guanidine HCl; (o), protein bound to W9F α A-crystallin. Quenching data were obtained at 25°C (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1996, 271, 10449 © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (Ref. 134)).

crystallin. A very similar trend is also obtained in the iodide quenching data¹³⁴.

The results provide crucial information about the conformational states recognized by α -crystallin. It captures non-native states characterized by a low degree of unfolding. Such aggregation prone conformers appear very early in the unfolding pathway. This function of α -crystallin is physiologically relevant for its chaperone function in the lens. Oxidative stress and ultraviolet radiation exposure to eye lens under physiological conditions is unlikely to cause extensive unfolding. But they can induce tertiary structural perturbations. Before further damage to the proteins occurs, these non-native intermediates are stabilized by α -crystallin. Such a function of α -crys-

tallin is fully consistent with its physiological role as a “junior chaperone” maintaining the transparency of the eye lens^{71,72}.

3.4. Secondary structure of substrate recognized by α -crystallin

A key to the understanding the molecular basis of substrate specificity of α -crystallin is to obtain important information regarding the secondary structure of bound substrates. Extracting secondary structural information of individual components in protein-protein complexes poses great experimental challenges and very limited techniques especially low resolution can be applied. Secondary structures of α -, β - and γ -crystallins are dominated by β -sheet structure. Amide I band in FTIR is particularly sensitive to the secondary structure of major β -sheet proteins¹³⁵⁻¹⁴⁰. Nevertheless, the contributions of the amide I bands of chaperone-substrate complex will overlap and it will be impossible to distinguish between the contribution from the substrate protein and that of chaperone α -crystallin. In order to resolve this problem we applied the strategy of “isotope-edited” infrared spectroscopy¹⁴¹⁻¹⁴³. We uniformly labeled α A-crystallin with ¹³C. This was accomplished through recombinant expression of α A-crystallin in *E. coli* using uniformly labeled ¹³C-labeled glucose in the culture as the sole carbon source¹⁴⁴. The labeling shifted the position of the main IR band from 1636 to 1591 cm^{-1} . This shift is consistent with the theoretical predictions and experimental results¹⁴¹⁻¹⁴³. The shift greatly reduced the overlapping between the conformation-sensitive amide I bands of labeled α -crystallin and unlabeled substrate proteins. The residual overlapping could be removed by subtracting the IR spectrum of the ¹³C-labeled α A-crystallin from the spectrum of the complex¹⁴⁴. The separated band at 1591 cm^{-1} served as a reliable marker for determining the subtraction factor. This procedure has allowed us to gain insight into the secondary structure of α -crystallin-bound species. We have used γ - and β -crystallin as substrate protein and studied their amide I band after complex formation with α -crystallin.

The amide I band of the native γ -crystallin having a maximum at 1636 cm^{-1} constitute overlapping components from different elements of protein secondary structure¹³⁸⁻¹⁴⁵. These components can be resolved by Fourier self-deconvolution^{138,145}. The deconvolved spectrum

Fig. 20. Infrared spectra of native γ -crystallin (trace 1), heat-treated γ -crystallin bound to α A-crystallin (trace 2), and γ -crystallin thermally denatured in the absence of the chaperone (trace 3) (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1999, 274, 33209. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. (Ref. 144)).

of the native γ -crystallin has a very strong characteristic β -sheet band at 1636 cm^{-1} (Fig. 20, trace 1). Other amide I component bands at 1656 cm^{-1} (α -helix), 1665 and 1686 cm^{-1} (turns) and 1673 cm^{-1} (β -sheet + turns) are much weaker. The fractional areas of these bands, representing estimate of protein secondary structure were determined by curve fitting procedure^{138,146}. The infrared spectrum of γ -crystallin bound to ^{13}C α -crystallin was obtained by subtracting the signal of ^{13}C -labeled α A-crystallin thermally treated in the same way as that in the complex from the spectrum of the protein protein complex¹⁴⁴. The amide I band contour of the chaperone-bound γ -crystallin is remarkably similar to that of the native protein in sharp contrast to that of the thermally unfolded γ -crystallin in absence of the chaperone. Upon deconvolution (Fig. 20, trace 2), the spectrum shows a dominant β -sheet band at 1634 cm^{-1} . Quantitative analysis indicates that the secondary structure of the chaperone bound γ -crystallin has slightly decreased content of β -sheet structure (approximately 61% versus 66% in the native protein), whereas the content of α -helical structure remains essentially unchanged¹⁴⁴ (Table 5).

A very similar trend was observed (Table 5) for another major β -sheet substrate protein β _L-crystallin. Compared with the native protein, the overall content of β -sheet structure in the bound β _L-crystallin is reduced from approximately 40 to 36% (Table 5). Overall our results

Table 5. The amide I component bands of γ and β _L-crystallins and their conformational assignment

Numbers in parentheses represent the fractional area of the individual bands

Protein	β -Sheet	Helix	Turns	Unordered
Native γ -crystallin	1636 (57%)	1656 (8%)	1663 (15%)	1645 (5%)
	1673 (9%) ^a		1686 (6%)	
Chaperone bound γ -crystallin	1634 (50%)	1656 (9%)	1662 (17%)	1644 (9%)
	1671 (11%) ^a		1682 (4%)	
Native β _L -crystallin	1631 (36%)	1655 (11%)	1666 (18%)	1643 (28%)
	1673 (4%) ^a		1682 (3%)	
Chaperone bound β _L -crystallin	1631 (29%)	1653 (9%)	1662 (13%)	1643 (34%)
	1670 (7%) ^a		1682 (5%)	

^aThis band may also contain contributions from turns.

show that the secondary structure of bound substrates is native like. Ours is the first ever report of secondary structure determination of substrate bound to the chaperone α -crystallin¹⁴⁴.

3.5. Subunit exchange and chaperone function of α -crystallin

α -Crystallin was found to be an effective chaperone for various substrate proteins whether related or not. But in the lens its major partners are β - and γ -crystallin and these are likely its natural substrates in the lens. The question whether α -crystallin has any specific affinity for its natural substrates over others interested us. We did a simple thermal aggregation assay with one natural (γ -crystallin) and one non-natural (carbonic anhydrase) substrates and compared the efficiency of recombinant α A- and α B-crystallin for their chaperone function¹⁴⁷. The results are shown in Fig. 21. We found that both α A- and α B-crystallin at one tenth of concentration of γ -crystallin could completely prevent its aggregation. α A-Crystallin required 1 : 1 concentration ratio to prevent the aggregation of carbonic anhydrase nearly completely. α B-Crystallin on the other hand at 1 : 1 ratio could not prevent the aggregation of carbonic anhydrase at all¹⁴⁷. The results suggest that α -crystallin has special affinity for its natural substrates and acts as extremely efficient chaperone against them. This observation suggested that a separate mechanism might be operative in the recognition between α -crystallin and its own substrate¹⁴⁷.

In order to elucidate the underlying mechanism that is responsible for the unusual behavior of α -crystallin we

Fig. 21. Chaperone activity of α -crystallin against natural and non-natural substrate. Carbonic anhydrase was used as non-natural substrate and γ -crystallin was used as natural substrate and the thermal assay for both substrates were carried out at 65°C. Left panel : α A-crystallin and right panel for α B-crystallin. Concentration of carbonic anhydrase or γ -crystallin in all the experiments were 0.2 mg/ml and the ratio of substrate to chaperone shown in the Figure are on (w/w) basis (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2007, 85, 189. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. (Ref. 147)).

studied the rate of subunit exchange of α -crystallin. We used a donor acceptor pair of fluorescence probes, namely AIAS and LYI to label recombinant human α A-crystallin which has one fully exposed cysteine residues at positions 131 and one buried cystein residue at 142. Only the exposed Cys132 residue was covalently modified. We carefully checked to verify that labeling did not change the oligomerization and chaperone properties of α A-crystallin. When LYI-labeled α A-crystallin were mixed at 37°C with the AIAS labeled one, because of the energy transfer between AIAS and LYI, we observed a time-dependent decrease in AIAS emission intensity at 415 nm and a concomitant increase in LYI fluorescence intensity at 525 nm. Subunit rate constant (k_r) was obtained by fitting the energy transfer data to the exponential equation

$$F(t)/F(0) = A + B \exp(-k_r t) \quad (3)$$

where $F(t)/F(0)$ denotes the fluorescence intensity ratio at time t and $t = 0$ and A and B are two constants.

Effect of bound substrates on the subunit exchange rate of α A-crystallin

We compared the subunit exchange rates of α A-crystallin when bound to its natural substrate γ -crystallin and non-natural substrate carbonic anhydrase (CA). The bound complexes were prepared by incubating separately AIAS

and LYI labeled α A-crystallin with either γ -crystallin or CA at 1 : 1 ratio at 65°C for 1 h and cooling down to the experimental temperature. The subunit exchange experiment was carried out at several temperatures ranging from 42–48°C. The kinetic profiles for γ -crystallin and CA bound α A-crystallin are shown in Fig. 22. It can be seen that higher decrease in AIAS fluorescence intensity was observed, when α A-crystallin was complexed with its natural substrate γ -crystallin than compared to non natural substrate CA (Figs. 22A and 22B). This suggests that binding of CA to α A-crystallin affected the subunit rate constant more than the binding of γ - to α A-crystallin.

Fig. 22. Effect of temperature on the subunit exchange of substrate bound α A-crystallin. (A) Measurements of subunit exchange between γ -crystallin bound AIAS-labeled and γ -crystallin bound LYI-labeled α A-crystallin at 42°C (●), 45°C (○) and 48°C (+). (B) Measurements of subunit exchange between CA bound AIAS-labeled and CA bound LYI-labeled α A-crystallin at 42°C (●), 45°C (○) and 48°C (+). First, complex was allowed to form by incubating separately different concentrations of each substrate protein with both 0.4 mg/ml AIAS-tagged and LYI-tagged α A-crystallin at 65°C for 1 h. The solutions were cooled back to 25°C for 1 h. Then we mixed equal amounts of AIAS-labeled and LYI-labeled α A-crystallin containing the bound substrate and measured relative emission intensity at 415 nm at different time intervals (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2007, 85, 189. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. (Ref. 147)).

The activation energy was calculated by Arrhenius equation^{11,98,147}

$$\ln(k_r) = \ln A - E_a/RT \quad (4)$$

where k_r is the subunit rate constant, A the pre exponential factor, T the absolute temperature in Kelvin scale, and E_a the activation energy for subunit exchange. The activation energy for subunit exchange for native, γ -crystallin bound, and CA bound α A-crystallin obtained from the plot of $\ln(k_r)$ against $1/T$ was given in Table 6. It was found that in absence of any bound substrate, the activation energy of α A-crystallin subunit exchange was 158

Table 6. Activation energy (E_a) for the subunit exchange reaction of recombinant human α A-crystallin in absence and presence of bound substrate (at ratio 1 : 1, w/w)

Bound substrate	Activation energy (kJ/mol)
None	158
Bovine γ -crystallin	193
Carbonic anhydrase	210

kJ/mol. On binding with its natural substrate γ -crystallin, the activation energy of subunit exchange was increased by $\sim 22\%$, whereas with CA, the enhancement of activation energy was $\sim 33\%$.

The results also indicate that subunit exchange may play an important role in helping of α -crystallin to discriminate between its natural and non-natural substrate. Chaperone activity is believed to be linked to the dynamics of the exchange process. It is interesting to mention here that complete prevention of aggregation of β - and γ -crystallin with 1/10th the amount of α -crystallin indicates that such a process may not involve static-binding which would require at least one α -crystallin subunit per molecule of substrate¹⁴⁷. Instead the interaction between α -crystallin and its own substrate may be very dynamic in which given α -crystallin subunit exchanging between different oligomers, may interact with its crystallin substrate for an extremely short duration before interacting with another substrate molecule. Because of the short residence time of the α -crystallin molecule on the substrate, it will be able to interact dynamically with a large number of substrate molecules in short time. This average time required for a subunit of α -crystallin to move from one substrate to another may be sufficiently short compared to the time required for collision between two substrate molecules initiating aggregation. For non natural substrates, substrate might have a high residence time on the chaperone surface. In this case, lack of sufficient amount of chaperone would cause aggregation.

We believe that the similarity of the secondary structure of α -, β - and γ -crystallin may be one of the reasons for such a distinctive behavior. CD and FTIR data have revealed that all the three proteins have dominant ($\sim 50\%$) β -sheet structure and very little α -helical structure^{60,144,148}. Because of the structural similarity both there is much less barrier to the subunit exchange facilitating the dynamic interaction mechanism. Non-native substrates having higher amount of helical structures creates greater obstruction for the β -sheet rich α -crystallin to exchange leading to higher residence time of the chaperone in bound complex. This leads to a static binding mechanism for the non-native substrate.

4. Small molecule and chaperone function of α -crystallin

4.1. Role of ATP on the chaperone function of α -crystallin

Adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP) is one of the best known small biomolecules, which stores readily available chemical energy in two of its phosphate bonds. The total quantity of ATP in human body is near about 0.1 mole. Its consumption in human body is followed by its biosynthesis in various pathways such as glycolysis¹⁴⁹, beta oxidation¹⁵⁰, oxidative phosphorylation¹⁵¹ etc. It is also a very important molecule in intracellular signal transduction pathways. Often the ratio between ATP and AMP acts as an energy sensor for a cell in controlling its metabolic pathways. It is very crucially involved in sustaining the cell structure by facilitating assembly and disassembly of elements of the cytoskeleton. ATP also acts as an extracellular signalling molecule which is recognised by the purinergic membrane receptors present in both central and peripheral nervous systems¹⁵². In synthesis of ribonucleic acid (RNA), RNA polymerase directly incorporates ATP into the molecule. Cleavage of the pyrophosphate bond of ATP provides the energy for driving this polymerization¹⁵³.

Since, ATP concentration in lens is extremely high¹⁵⁴ (> 6 mM), the role of ATP in the chaperone function of α -crystallin has been widely studied^{103-106,155}. Many well known classical chaperones of the large heat shock protein family, including GroEL, DnaK etc. function in an ATP dependent manner¹⁵⁶. Hydrolysis of ATP plays a crucial role in dissociating the chaperone substrate complex and thus enhance the chaperone mediated folding of substrate proteins.

However, such an activity had been less well documented in α -crystallin system¹⁵⁷. The autophosphorylation activity of α -crystallin reported by some workers^{158,159} had been debated by others¹⁵⁷. Some enhancement of chaperone activity and refolding yield of unfolded enzymes was reported^{103–106} in presence of ATP. Some spectroscopic^{104,155} and proteolytic studies¹⁶⁰ suggested possible interaction between ATP and α -crystallin but its functional implications were far from clear. Molecular mechanism of the ATP effect was also debated. Some believed that ATP destabilized the chaperone-substrate complex much the same way as in GroEL system^{103,106} while others argued that most sHSPs having the conserved ' α -crystallin domain' had no dependence on ATP for their functions⁹.

In view of the above background the role of high concentration of ATP in the eye lens remained a mystery. We studied the problem in detail in our laboratory¹¹². We incubated at 37°C the chaperone α -crystallin with its substrate γ -crystallin in presence and absence of ATP and passed the mixture through a 100 kDa membrane filter. γ -Crystallin freely passed through the membrane in absence of ATP but was retained to the extent of ~50% in presence of 3 mM ATP indicating complex formation between α -crystallin and γ -crystallin. There was no association at 25°C but association increased with increase of temperature. The binding isotherm at physiological temperature of 37°C and the Scatchard analysis of the data (Fig. 1B) revealed that the association is of low affinity ($K_d \sim 3\text{--}10 \mu\text{M}$). The association in presence of ATP was also demonstrated by gel filtration chromatography using γ -crystallin covalently labeled with a highly fluorescence probe FITC and monitoring FITC fluorescence (Fig. 23). While free γ -crystallin eluted at 22 min, incubation of γ -crystallin with α -crystallin in presence of ATP above 37°C reduced the peak at 22 min and a new peak at 10 min appeared confirming the high molecular mass associated complex of γ -crystallin with α -crystallin. Thus contrary to the common belief that ATP causes dissociation of the chaperone-substrate complex it actually induces complex formation at the physiological temperature. Replacing the α -crystallin with BSA showed no association with α -crystallin in presence of ATP indicating the presence of chaperone is required for this interaction¹¹².

The association occurs through additional exposure of hydrophobic sites on the chaperone surface. This was

Fig. 23. ATP induced association between substrate and α A-crystallin at different temperatures, determined by gel filtration method FITC tagged γ -crystallin (0.25 mg/ml) and human α A-crystallin (0.25 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 were incubated with or without 3 mM ATP or ATP- γ -S for 1 h at various temperature. The mixture was brought to 25°C and then 20 μ l of it was injected to the column pre-equilibrated with the same buffer with or without 3 mM ATP or ATP- γ -S. Trace 1, no ATP, 25°C, trace 2, + ATP, 25°C, trace 3, no ATP 37°C, trace 4, + ATP, 37°C, trace 5, + ATP- γ -S, 37°C (This research was originally published in *J Biol Chem*, 2004, 279, 42648 © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (Ref 112))

clearly shown by our measurement of surface hydrophobicity of α -crystallin using a conformation sensitive hydrophobic probe bis-ANS, which strongly fluoresces on binding to hydrophobic pockets but otherwise practically nonfluorescent. We showed¹¹² that ATP opened up additional hydrophobic sites on α -crystallin surface, but not on the substrate protein γ -crystallin or carbonic anhydrase (Fig. 24). The enhancement of surface hydrophobicity of α -crystallin in presence of ATP is consistent with the increase in its chaperone-like activity as measured by enhanced aggregation prevention ability and also enhanced the refolding yield of lactate dehydrogenase from unfolded state (Figs. 25A and B)

Thus our results showed that instead of dissociating the complex, ATP holds them gently together. Both α -crystallin and substrate remain associated in native-like conformation¹¹². Mchaourab and coworkers in a series of papers^{161–164} demonstrated that α -crystallin can bind to native-like degenerate states of substrate proteins. ATP binding causes minor conformational changes stabilizing

Fig. 24. Bis-ANS binding to various α -crystallin and its substrate γ -crystallin in the presence (open symbols) and absence (closed symbols) of 3 mM ATP (A) α A-Crystallin, 37°C, (B) α B-crystallin, 37°C and (C) γ -crystallin, 37°C. Protein concentration in all samples was 50 μ g/ml in 50 μ M phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. Excitation wavelength of 390 nm and emission wavelength of 490 nm were used (This research was originally published in *J Biol Chem*, 2004, 279, 42648 © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (Ref 112))

the α -crystallin structure by ~ 4.5 kJ/mol (Table 7). ATP induced shifting of free energy triggers the binding between the α -crystallin and its substrate. We also showed that binding of ATP to α -crystallin and not its hydrolysis is required for all these effects, as replacement of ATP by its non-hydrolyzable analogue adenosine-5'-O-(3-thiophosphate) i.e. ATP- γ S (Fig. 1C and D) produced same result. This is quite contrary to the chaperone GroEL for whose function the hydrolysis of ATP is required¹⁵⁶. At the physiological concentration of 6 mM ATP in the lens, most of the substrate proteins remain associated with the chaperone α -crystallin. This association is physiologically significant for two reasons; (1) the association ensures that when a substrate tends to unfold it has less chance to form intermolecular aggregate which is detrimental to lens transparency; (2) association is crucial for dense packing of proteins in the lens to form the refractive medium. Thus, our work led to the foundation towards the understanding of ATP independent chaperone mechanism of small heat shock proteins.

4.2. Influence of Zn^{2+} binding on the structure and stability of α -crystallin

Zinc is typically the second most abundant transition metal in organisms after iron and it is the only metal

Fig. 25. Enhancement of chaperone activity of α B-crystallin induced by ATP (A), Insulin aggregation assay at 37°C, trace 1, 0.35 mg/ml insulin alone, trace 2, + 0.175 mg/ml α B-crystallin, trace 3, + 0.175 mg/ml α B-crystallin + 3 mM ATP. All solutions contained 20 mM DTT (B), Time course of reactivation of LDH at 37°C from 6 M GdnHCl solution in the presence and absence of 3 mM ATP. Trace 1, 10 nM LDH alone, trace 2, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin, trace 3, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM ATP, trace 4, 10 nM LDH + 30 μ M α B-crystallin + 3 mM ATP. Refolding was initiated by 100-fold dilution of LDH (1 μ M) in 6 M GdnHCl in a refolding buffer (50 mM phosphate, pH 7.2) containing 10 mM magnesium acetate and 5 mM DTT. Each data point is the average of triplicate measurements, and error bar denotes the standard deviation (This research was originally published in *J Biol Chem*, 2004, 279, 42648 © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (Ref 112))

Table 7. Parameters of equilibrium urea unfolding of human α A-crystallin in absence and presence of ATP at 37°C, obtained from the three state model ($N \rightleftharpoons I \rightleftharpoons U$) fit

Systems studied	ΔG_1° (kJ/mol)	ΔG_2° (kJ/mol)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)	m_1 kJ/(mol M)	m_2 kJ/(mol M)
Human α A	6.43 \pm 0.44	13.51 \pm 0.89	19.94 \pm 0.67	2.77 \pm 0.21	5.33 \pm 0.35
Human α A + 3 mM ATP	8.27 \pm 0.55	16.17 \pm 0.88	24.44 \pm 0.72	2.81 \pm 0.38	5.75 \pm 0.43

which appears in all enzyme classes¹⁶⁵. In human body there is about 2-4 g of zinc distributed throughout the human body¹⁶⁶. Most of the zinc concentration is found in the brain, muscle, bones, kidney and liver¹⁶⁷. It aids proteins in rapidly shifting conformations to perform biological reactions¹⁶⁸. Zinc serves a purely structural role in zinc fingers, twists and clusters. Zinc fingers form parts of some transcription factors, which are proteins that recognize DNA base sequences during the replication and transcription of DNA.

This bivalent metal ion has also been detected in the lens, retina and other parts of the eye¹⁶⁹⁻¹⁷¹. *In vivo*, human lens contains 21 μ g zinc per g dry weight of the adult lens. Because of high content of zinc inside eye, scientists performed *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments to get an idea about the impact of zinc on different parts of eye like lens, retina etc. Zinc deficiency has been reported to produce cataract in sea fish such as trout or salmon¹⁷²⁻¹⁷⁴. Doctors for treatment of degenerative eye diseases^{175,176} prescribe zinc supplements but experimental results could not establish clear evidences for its beneficial effect¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁸¹. Some studies even cautioned against the wide spread use of zinc supplements¹⁸³. Experimental evidences also indicate that interaction between zinc and α -crystallin take place *in vitro*. For example, Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have been reported to induce expression of

α B-crystallin in human lens epithelial cells¹⁸⁴. Cu^{2+} has been suggested to play redox or structuring center and Zn^{2+} was considered to act as a Lewis acid and play structural role¹⁸⁵. Recently, Coi *et al.*¹⁸⁶ proposed a molecular model for the most probable coordination site for Zn^{2+} in α B-crystallin.

We studied the effect of Zn^{2+} and many other bivalent metal ions on the chaperone function of α -crystallin by insulin aggregation assay¹¹⁹. The results presented in Fig. 26 show that Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} at 1 mM concentration has very little influence on the chaperone function of α -crystallin but Zn^{2+} resulted in significance enhancement in chaperone function. Some minor enhancement was also observed in presence of Cu^{2+} (unpublished result). Similar trend is also observed in the refolding assay of chaperone activity measuring the percentage enzyme activity recovered by the chaperone in presence of the divalent ions (Fig. 27). This enhancement of chaperone activity in presence of Zn^{2+} was consistent with the enhancement of surface hydrophobic exposure as measured by binding of hydrophobic probe TNS (Fig. 28). Being a paramagnetic ion, Cu^{2+} caused substantial quenching of TNS fluorescence¹¹⁹. This enhancement of hydrophobicity revealed that α -crystallin close to its surface has a reserve of extra hydrophobic residues, which relocates at the surface on ionic perturbation¹¹⁹.

Fig. 26. Effect of 1 mM bivalent metal ions on the chaperone activity of α -crystallin. (A) Chaperone activity of α A-crystallin and (B) chaperone activity of α B-crystallin : (1) insulin only, (2) insulin and α -crystallin, (3) insulin, α -crystallin, and Ca, (4) insulin, α -crystallin, and Mg, (5) insulin, α -crystallin, and Pb, (6) insulin, α -crystallin, and Cd, (7) insulin, α -crystallin, and Co, (8) insulin, α -crystallin, and Fe, (9) insulin, α -crystallin, and Ni, (10) insulin, α -crystallin, and Cu, and (11) insulin, α -crystallin, and Zn. The assay mixture (600 μ l) contained 50 mM Tris buffer (pH 7.0), 100 mM NaCl, 0.32 mg/mL insulin, 1 mM bivalent metal ions, and 0.128 mg/mL α A-crystallin or 0.08 mg/mL α B-crystallin, and aggregation was started by adding 25 mM β ME (This research was originally published in *Biochemistry*, 2008, 47, 804. © the American Chemical Society. (Ref. 119)).

Fig. 27. Time course of reactivation of LDH at 37°C from an 8 M urea solution in the presence and absence of different bivalent metal ions at 1 mM. LDH was inactivated by incubation at 25°C in an 8 M urea solution at 8 h. Refolding was initiated by 100-fold dilution of LDH (1 μ M) in 8 M urea in a refolding buffer [50 mM Tris containing 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.0)] containing 10 mM magnesium acetate, 10 mM β ME, 30 μ M α B-crystallin, and/or different bivalent metal ions at 1 mM. Each data point is the average of triplicate measurement, and error bars denote the standard deviation (This research was originally published in *Biochemistry*, 2008, 47, 804. © the American Chemical Society. (Ref. 119)).

Fig. 28. Fluorescence spectra of TNS bound to α B-crystallin in the absence and presence of 1 mM bivalent metal ions at 25°C. The protein concentration was 0.1 mg/mL and the TNS concentration 100 μ M. All protein solutions were first incubated with different bivalent metal ions at 1 mM for 1 h and then incubated with TNS for 2 h. The fluorescence spectrum of different samples was taken from 350 to 520 nm. The excitation wavelength was 320 nm : (a) Cu, (b) Fe, (c) Co, (d) Ni, (e) Mg, (f) no bivalent metal ion, (g) Ca, (h) Cd, (i) Pb, and (j) Zn (This research was originally published in *Biochemistry*, 2008, 47, 804. © the American Chemical Society. (Ref. 119)).

This additional exposure of hydrophobic pockets was not due to partial unfolding but due to side chain reorientation to coordinate to bivalent metal ion. We measured the thermodynamic stability of α -crystallin in presence of Zn^{2+} by equilibrium unfolding in presence of increasing concentration of denaturant urea¹¹⁹ (Fig. 29). The transition mid-points in the denaturation profile shifted to higher urea concentrations in presence of Zn^{2+} indicating in-

Fig. 29. Equilibrium urea unfolding profile of α B-crystallin in the absence and presence of different bivalent metal ions at 1 mM and 25°C : (1) α B-crystallin alone, (2) α B-crystallin and 1 mM Ca^{2+} , (3) α B-crystallin and 1 mM Cu^{2+} , (4) α B-crystallin and 0.1 mM Zn^{2+} , and (5) α B-crystallin and 1 mM Zn^{2+} . The protein concentration was 0.1 mg/mL. The profile has been normalized to a scale of 0–1. Symbols represent the experimental data points, and the solid lines represent the best fit to a three-state model described by eq. (2) (This research was originally published in *Biochemistry*, 2008, 47, 804. © the American Chemical Society. (Ref. 119)).

crease in stability of the chaperone structure. A three state model analyzed the profiles and the thermodynamic stability in terms of free energy change to unfold the protein determined. Zn^{2+} ions caused substantial increase in thermodynamic stability from 23 kJ/mol to 58 kJ/mol. Cu^{2+} ions resulted in moderate enhancement of stability to \sim 40 kJ/mol (unpublished data). These results show that Zn^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions may play a very important role in modulating the stability of α -crystallin in the lens.

The effect of Zn^{2+} on the properties of α -crystallin was due to binding of the ions to α -crystallin. This was demonstrated by MALDI mass spectrometry of intact protein¹²⁰. The m/z for the singly charged ion shifted from 19914 to 20145 for α A-crystallin and from 20161

to 20370 for α B-crystallin (Fig. 30). On an average, each α -crystallin subunit bound 3–4 numbers of Zn^{2+} ions. The doubly charged ion of α -crystallin resolved the various peaks arising from binding of 1–5 Zn^{2+} ions. We showed that this binding is specific to Zn^{2+} (and Cu^{2+} , unpublished) only and other ions do not show similar behavior (Fig. 31) The binding of Zn^{2+} ions stabilized the oligomeric structures of α -crystallin. This was shown from the measurement of oligomeric size in urea solution by DLS. Our results showed that in absence of Zn^{2+} (or Cu^{2+}), the oligomeric structure broke down above 3 M urea, while in their presence the structure remained intact even at 5 M urea.

The binding of multiple Zn^{2+} or Cu^{2+} ions to one subunit of α -crystallin is interesting. α -Crystallin is not known to have any Zn^{2+} finger motif in its sequence. Sequence analysis by an improved method according to Shu *et al.*¹⁸⁶ predicts that none of α A- and α B-crystallin

Fig. 30. MALDI mass spectra of intact recombinant human α A-crystallin and α B-crystallin in absence and presence of Zn^{2+} . A α A-Crystallin in absence (blue line) and in presence (red line) of 20-fold molar excess Zn^{2+} ions B α B-Crystallin in absence (black line) and in presence (red line) of 20-fold molar excess Zn^{2+} ions Inset shows doubly charged (M2H⁺) species of α A- (Panel A) and α B-crystallin (Panel B) in presence of Zn^{2+} ions Protein solution (1 mg/mL) in ammonium bicarbonate buffer was mixed with 1 mM Zn^{2+} ions and incubated at room temperature for 1 h before mixing with matrix Nonacidic matrix DHAP was mixed in 1 : 1 ratio with the sample and then spotted on MALDI target plate (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2011, 95, 105 © Wiley Periodicals, Inc (Ref 120))

Fig. 31. MALDI TOF mass spectra of α B-crystallin with different bivalent metal ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) Doubly charged (M2H⁺) and singly charged (MH⁺) species of bivalent metal bound states of α B-crystallin before and after incubation with 20-fold molar excess different bivalent metal ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) 1 mg/mL protein solution in ammonium bicarbonate buffer incubated with 1 mM metal ions and incubated at room temperature for 1 h before mixing with matrix DHAP (This research was originally published in *Biopolymers*, 2011, 95, 105 © Wiley Periodicals, Inc (Ref 120))

would bind to metal ion such as Zn^{2+} as no such binding pocket exists. The stabilization of the oligomeric structure by these metal ions means that the inter-subunit contacts rather than the subunit domain structure must have stabilized. It therefore appeared likely that these metal ions might be involved in intersubunit bridging α -Crystallin is known to undergo subunit exchange between oligomers. We measured the subunit exchange rates of α -crystallin in presence of Zn^{2+} ions Our results show that in presence of Zn^{2+} ions the subunit exchange rates are drastically reduced. The results clearly suggest that Zn^{2+} ions are involved in intersubunit bridging These results also throw light on another aspect of chaperone function Many groups have linked chaperone activity to subunit exchange suggesting direct relationship between structural dynamics and chaperone activity^{11,18,95,187} Results to the contrary are also abundant in the literature Augusteyn *et al.*¹⁸⁸ showed that α -crystallin oligomers crosslinked with glutaraldehyde possessed higher chaperone activity than native α -crystallin Our results showed that although Zn^{2+} ions have arrested subunit exchange, chaperone activity of α -crystallin is enhanced in presence of Zn^{2+} . We believe that although subunit exchange pro-

vides a valid mechanism for α -crystallin to distinguish between its natural and non-natural substrate, chaperone action is possible even when the subunit exchange rate is highly compromised. Our results strongly support the notion that chaperone action is a surface phenomenon because there is always positive correlation between exposed surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity¹²⁰.

We believe that our results not only show the importance of ionic interactions in the structure and stability of the chaperone α -crystallin, it also shows the micro-regulation of such function by some ions. Our results establish for the first time the beneficial role of Zn^{2+} in the eye giving scientific rationale for the use of Zn^{2+} supplement for eye related problems.

4.3. Effect of methylglyoxal on the chaperone function α -crystallin

Several post translational modified adducts accumulate inside the eye lens during aging and such accumulations lead to the cataract formation. Various independent studies revealed that different post translational modifications decreased the chaperone function of α -crystallin which might be the molecular basis for the cataract formation during aging¹⁸⁹⁻¹⁹³. Large amount of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) were found in aged lens which suggest that among different post translational modification processes, glycation is the major one. Glycation is the non-enzymatic reaction of carbohydrates especially glucose with proteins. First, glucose and other sugars react with amino groups of proteins to form unstable Schiff's base adduct and then slowly undergoes rearrangement to form relatively stable Amadori products. Through a series of parallel and sequential reactions (often termed as "Maillard reaction"), these Amadori products form many advanced glycation end products (AGEs), some of which are fluorescent and colored^{194,195}.

Lens contains $\sim 1-2 \mu\text{M}$ of methylglyoxal (MGO). MGO is derived *in vivo* mostly from triose phosphate intermediates of glycolysis by non-enzymatic mechanisms¹⁹⁶. It is the major precursor of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) in different tissues¹⁹⁷. MGO, a α -dicarbonyl compound, reacts with lysine, arginine and histidine residues in proteins^{198,199} and forms fluorescent advanced glycation end products such as hydroimidazolone^{200,201}, argpyrimidine^{202,203}, methylglyoxal lysine

dimer²⁰⁴⁻²⁰⁶ (MOLD) etc. Padayatti *et al.* reported that cataractous aged lens contains more of these MGO derived AGEs than the normal lens²⁰⁷.

This above finding suggests that MGO modification may be harmful for lens transparency. Surprisingly, Nagaraj's group has demonstrated that when MGO derived AGEs (especially argpyrimidine) were formed on α A-crystallin, its chaperone function enhanced dramatically²⁰⁸. During MGO treatment, they also pinpointed such arginine residues (converted to argpyrimidine). Arginine residue in protein loses its positive charge while it converts into argpyrimidine and hydroimidazolone. With the aid of mutational study, they further proved that the neutralization of positive charge of pin-pointed arginine residues on α A-crystallin is crucial for the enhancement of the chaperone function of this protein²⁰⁹. In addition, MGO modification of homoarginine (arginine-like structure) led to enhanced chaperone function of α A-crystallin as well²¹⁰. An independent study indicated the presence of hydroimidazolone in the lens proteins²⁰⁰. Recently, Gangadhariah *et al.*²¹¹ showed that hydroimidazolone modification of α A-crystallin also enhanced its chaperone function. On contrary, Reddy's group^{212,213} reported that MGO modification decreased the chaperone function of α -crystallin. In our laboratory, we also found the similar trends²¹⁴. Our studies showed that methylglyoxal modification (0.1–10 mM) caused significant decrease in chaperone function of α -crystallin as reflected both in thermal aggregation assay and enzyme refolding assay. This was accompanied by the decrease in surface hydrophobicity and subtle changes in secondary structure of α -crystallin. Significant cross-linking was also observed due to methylglyoxal modification of human α -crystallin. With 10 mM MGO modification (for 72 h) the thermodynamic stability of α -crystallin decreased from 21.6 kJ/mol to 10.4 kJ/mol (Table 1). All these findings in the literature suggests that mild modification of α -crystallin with MGO ($< 100 \mu\text{M}$) leads to the enhancement in the chaperone function of this protein which may be important in maintaining the transparency of human eye lens. On the other hand, modification with higher amount of MGO ($> 100 \mu\text{M}$), α -crystallin loses its protection ability which may leads to the cataract formation during aging.

Concluding remarks

The specificity of α -crystallin is different from that of

classical chaperones. α -Crystallin binds substrate proteins in native-like conformation in the early intermediate stage while GroEL binds intermediates located at higher reaction coordinates. Function of α -crystallin is ATP independent. Modification by methylglyoxal has adverse effect on the structure and function of α -crystallin. Zn^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions can modulate the structure and function of α -crystallin. Loss of these ions from lens could lead to development of cataract or related problems. The locations of the binding sites of these ions in α -crystallin are yet to be identified. Investigation in this regard is already in progress in our laboratory.

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